

TEACHERS' PARTICIPATION IN SCHOOL-BASED DECISION-MAKING IN DISCIPLINE, SPORTS AND TIMETABLE SCHEDULING AS PREDICTORS OF EFFECTIVE ADMINISTRATION OF PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RIVERS STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study examined teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in discipline, sports and games, and timetable scheduling as predictors of effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 335 principals and 5,912 teachers from public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, giving a total of 6,247 respondents across the 23 Local Government Areas. A sample size of 760 respondents was used, consisting of 168 principals (50% of principals' population) and 592 teachers (10% of teachers' population). The stratified and simple random sampling techniques were employed to ensure fair representation of respondents. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled 'Teachers' Participation in School-Based Decision-Making in Discipline, Sports and Timetable Scheduling and Effective Administration Questionnaire (TPSBDMDSSEAQ)'. The instrument contained two sections: Section 'A' covered demographic information, while Section 'B' contained items designed on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from Very High Extent (4) to Very Low Extent (1). The instrument was validated by experts in Educational Management. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha through a test-retest method, yielding a reliability coefficient of .888, indicating high internal consistency. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions, with a criterion mean of 2.50. Independent t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at a .05 level of significance. All analyses were carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28. The study provided empirical evidence on the extent of teachers' participation in decision-making and its implications for effective school administration in Rivers State. Recommendations were proffered.

Keywords: Teachers' Participation, School-Based Decision-Making, School Discipline, Sports And Games, Timetable Scheduling, Effective Administration, Public Senior Secondary Schools, Rivers State.

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INTRODUCTION

The growing complexity of educational administration in secondary schools has increased the need for inclusive and participatory management practices. One such approach is school-based decision-making, which emphasizes decentralization and the active involvement of key stakeholders, particularly teachers, in shaping school policies and practices. Teachers occupy a central position in the school system as they interact directly with students and implement curricular and co-curricular activities. Their participation in decision-making processes is therefore critical to achieving effective school administration. According to Ololube (2017), teacher involvement in decision-making enhances organizational effectiveness and promotes a sense of professional commitment among staff.

Teachers' participation in school-based decision-making refers to their involvement in determining policies and actions that affect the day-to-day functioning of the school. This participation spans several domains, including discipline, sports and games, and timetable scheduling. When teachers are involved in these areas, it promotes shared responsibility, improves communication, and strengthens the overall administrative structure of the school. Ololube (2017) argued that participatory decision-making at the school level leads to improved school climate and better administrative outcomes.

In the area of school discipline, teachers play a vital role due to their close interaction with students. Their involvement in disciplinary decision-making ensures that rules and regulations are practical, fair, and responsive to students' behavioral needs. Effective discipline contributes significantly to creating a conducive learning environment, which is essential for academic success. When teachers participate in designing and implementing disciplinary measures, it enhances consistency and reduces conflicts within the school system. As noted by Özdemir (2024), teacher participation in decision-making strengthens institutional practices and promotes accountability in school management.

Similarly, teachers' participation in decisions concerning sports and games is crucial for promoting students' holistic development. Co-curricular activities such as sports contribute to physical fitness, teamwork, and social development. Teachers, who often serve as coaches and coordinators, possess practical knowledge that can improve the planning and execution of these activities. Their involvement ensures that sports programmes are inclusive, well-organized, and aligned with educational goals. Furthermore, participatory decision-making in this domain enhances collaboration among staff and supports effective school administration (Epstein, 2011).

Timetable scheduling is another essential aspect of school administration that benefits from teachers' participation. The timetable serves as the operational framework for teaching and learning activities, influencing workload distribution, instructional time, and resource allocation. When teachers are involved in timetable planning, it promotes fairness, reduces scheduling conflicts, and ensures alignment with curriculum requirements. This collaborative approach enhances efficiency and contributes to the smooth running of the school. According to Cherotich, et al. (2023), teachers' participation in decision-making is positively associated with improved school outcomes, including academic performance and administrative effectiveness.

In spite of the recognized benefits of participatory decision-making, evidence suggests that teachers are not always adequately involved in school governance. In many public secondary schools, administrative decisions are often centralized, limiting teachers' contributions to key areas of school management. This lack of involvement can lead to low morale, reduced commitment, and inefficiencies in school administration. Ololube (2017) further noted that

limited participation may hinder the successful implementation of educational policies and reforms.

In Rivers State, Nigeria, public senior secondary schools face numerous administrative challenges, including issues related to discipline, coordination of co-curricular activities, and effective timetable management. These challenges highlight the need for more inclusive management approaches that leverage the expertise and experience of teachers (Ololube, 2024). Therefore, examining teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the areas of discipline, sports and games, and timetable scheduling is essential for understanding how these factors predict effective administration.

Statement of the Problem

Effective administration of public senior secondary schools remains a major concern in Rivers State, Nigeria, because many schools continue to experience challenges related to poor discipline, weak coordination of co-curricular activities and ineffective timetable scheduling. These issues often result in disruptions to teaching and learning, reduced student performance, and overall inefficiency in school management. In spite of the critical role teachers play in implementing school policies and interacting directly with students, their level of participation in school-based decision-making appears to be limited or inadequately utilized.

In many cases, administrative decisions in areas such as discipline, sports and games, and timetable scheduling are centralized in the hands of school principals, with little input from teachers. This lack of involvement may lead to impractical decisions, low teacher morale, and poor commitment to policy implementation. Consequently, the potential benefits of participatory decision-making, such as improved collaboration, accountability and administrative effectiveness are not fully realized.

Although existing studies have highlighted the importance of teachers' participation in decision-making, there is limited empirical evidence specifically examining how such participation in key functional areas predicts effective administration in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This gap creates the need for this study.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study examined teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in discipline, sports and timetable scheduling as predictors of effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the study tends to achieve the following objectives:

- To determine the extent teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school discipline enhances effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- To examine the extent teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of sports and games enhances effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- To evaluate the extent teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school Time-table schedules enhances effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- To what extent does teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school discipline enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- To what extent does teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of sports and games enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- To what extent does teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school Time-table schedules enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study in line with the objectives and tested at .05 level of significance:

- There is no significant difference in the mean rating of principals and teachers on the extent teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school discipline enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- There is no significant difference in the mean rating of principals and teachers on the extent teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of sports and games enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- There is no significant difference in the mean rating of principals and teachers on the extent teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school Time-table schedules enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Distributed Leadership Theory

Distributed Leadership Theory is a modern leadership approach that emphasizes the sharing of leadership responsibilities among multiple individuals within an organization rather than concentrating authority in a single person (Spillane, 2006). In the context of schools, this theory suggests that leadership functions should be distributed among principals, teachers, department heads, and other stakeholders to improve decision-making, collaboration, and organizational effectiveness. The theory is particularly relevant to educational settings where complex tasks require collective expertise and shared responsibility.

One of the major proponents of Distributed Leadership Theory is James P. Spillane, who argues that leadership is not the act of an individual leader but rather a product of interactions

among people and their situations. According to Ololube (2024), leadership emerges from the collaborative practices of multiple actors working together to achieve common goals. This perspective shifts attention away from the traditional “heroic leader” model to a more inclusive system where leadership is a shared activity embedded in organizational structures.

In schools, Distributed Leadership Theory implies that teachers are not merely implementers of decisions made by principals but active participants in leadership processes. This includes involvement in curriculum planning, discipline management, sports organization, and timetable scheduling. In distributing leadership roles, schools tap into the expertise and experience of teachers, thereby improving the quality of decisions and enhancing school effectiveness. Research has shown that distributed leadership contributes to improved instructional practices, stronger professional collaboration, and better student outcomes (Leithwood & Mascall, 2008).

A key assumption of Distributed Leadership Theory is that leadership is a practice rather than a position. This means that leadership functions are embedded in daily interactions and routines within the school. Teachers, for example, may lead in areas such as mentoring students, coordinating extracurricular activities, or participating in school committees. This shared responsibility enhances organizational capacity and reduces the burden on school principals, allowing for more efficient administration.

Furthermore, Distributed Leadership Theory promotes collaboration and professional learning communities within schools. When leadership is shared, teachers are more likely to engage in dialogue, exchange ideas, and support one another in solving educational problems. This collaborative culture fosters innovation and improves school performance. Harris (2013) emphasizes that distributed leadership strengthens school improvement efforts by building collective responsibility and trust among staff members.

In addition, the theory enhances teacher motivation and job satisfaction. When teachers are given leadership roles, they feel valued and empowered, which increases their commitment to school goals. This sense of ownership leads to higher levels of engagement and accountability. However, effective distributed leadership requires a supportive school culture, clear communication structures, and strong coordination to prevent confusion or role overlap.

In spite of its benefits, the implementation of Distributed Leadership Theory face challenges such as resistance from traditional leadership structures, lack of trust, and inadequate training. In some schools, principals may be reluctant to share authority, while some teachers may lack the confidence or skills to take on leadership roles. Therefore, successful implementation requires capacity building and a shift in organizational culture.

The relevance of this theory to this study, Distributed Leadership Theory provides a useful framework for understanding how shared leadership practices can improve school effectiveness. By involving teachers and other stakeholders in decision-making processes, schools can enhance collaboration, improve administrative efficiency, and promote sustainable school improvement.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Teachers' Participation in School-Based Decision-Making in the Area of School Discipline and Effective Administration

Teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in school discipline plays a significant role in enhancing the effective administration of public senior secondary schools (Bush, 2015; Ololube, 2017). The extent of such participation often determines how well disciplinary policies are formulated, implemented, and sustained within the school system. School discipline is central to administration because it shapes the learning environment, influences student behaviour, and affects overall school climate. When teachers are actively involved in disciplinary decisions, schools tend to experience improved orderliness, fairness, and administrative efficiency (Emmer et al., 2015).

To a large extent, teachers' participation enhances discipline through the development of realistic and workable policies. Teachers interact daily with students and possess firsthand knowledge of behavioural patterns and challenges. Their contributions help ensure that disciplinary rules are practical and applicable in real classroom contexts. This reduces the likelihood of ineffective or overly rigid policies that are difficult to enforce. According to Cotton (2000) and Ololube (2017), schools that involve teachers in decision-making tend to develop more effective and context-relevant policies.

Furthermore, teachers' involvement promotes consistency in the enforcement of disciplinary rules. When teachers participate in decision-making, they develop a sense of ownership and responsibility toward school policies. This encourages uniform application of disciplinary measures, which enhances fairness and predictability in the school system. Students are more likely to comply with rules when they perceive them as just and consistently enforced. Hoy and Miskel (2013) emphasized that participatory management fosters commitment and consistency in policy implementation, thereby improving administrative effectiveness.

To a moderate extent, teachers' participation also enhances communication and collaboration among staff, which is essential for effective administration. Discipline management requires coordinated efforts between teachers and school administrators. When teachers are involved in disciplinary committees or policy discussions, it promotes shared understanding and reduces conflicts. This collaborative approach ensures that disciplinary actions are supported by all stakeholders, leading to smoother administrative processes (Bush, 2015).

In addition, teachers' participation contributes to improved student-teacher relationships, which are vital for maintaining discipline. Teachers who are involved in decision-making are more likely to adopt supportive and corrective strategies rather than purely punitive measures. This fosters mutual respect and trust between teachers and students, leading to better compliance with school rules. A positive school climate, built on strong interpersonal relationships, significantly enhances administrative effectiveness (Emmer & Sabornie, 2015).

However, the extent of teachers' participation is not always optimal. In some public senior secondary schools, decision-making is centralized, limiting teachers' involvement to the implementation stage. This reduces their sense of ownership and may lead to inconsistent enforcement of disciplinary policies. Moreover, the absence of functional participatory structures, such as disciplinary committees, further restricts meaningful teacher involvement. To Cotton (2000), limited participation in decision-making can negatively affect teacher morale and the successful implementation of school policies.

Therefore, teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in school discipline enhances effective administration to a large extent. It leads to the development of practical policies, consistent enforcement of rules, improved collaboration, and stronger student-teacher relationships (Ololube, 2017). Ololube (2024) however stated that maximizing the benefits participation in school-based decision-making requires deliberate efforts to create inclusive decision-making structures and empower teachers to contribute meaningfully to school governance.

Teachers' Participation in School-Based Decision-Making in the Area of Sports and Games and Effective Administration

Teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in sports and games significantly enhances the effective administration of public senior secondary schools. Sports and games are important components of the school programme; it does not only contribute to students' physical development but also improves their social, emotional and moral growth. The extent to which teachers are involved in making decisions regarding these activities often determines how effectively such programmes are organized and managed. When teachers actively participate in decisions related to planning, implementation, and evaluation of sports activities, it strengthens administrative processes and promotes overall school effectiveness (Hoy & Miskel, 2013).

To a large extent, teachers' participation enhances effective administration through improved planning and organization of sports programmes. Teachers, who frequently serve as coaches, trainers, and supervisors, possess practical knowledge about students' abilities, interests, and available resources. Teachers' involvement ensures that decisions regarding sports schedules, facilities and participation are realistic and inclusive. This leads to well-structured programmes that align with the school's educational objectives. According to Bucher et al. (2016), effective management of school sports depends largely on collaborative planning involving those directly engaged in programme implementation.

Furthermore, teachers' involvement in decision-making is capable of promoting efficiency in the utilization of resources. Sports and games require proper allocation of time, equipment, and facilities. When teachers contribute to decisions about resource management, it reduces wastage and ensures equitable distribution. Their firsthand experience helps administrators make informed choices regarding procurement and maintenance of sports equipment. This collaborative approach enhances accountability and transparency, which are essential for effective school administration (Bush, 2015).

To a moderate extent, teachers' participation in sports-related decision-making fosters collaboration and teamwork among staff. Sports activities often require coordinated efforts among multiple teachers and departments. When teachers are involved in decision-making processes, it encourages open communication, shared responsibility, and mutual support. This collaborative environment reduces conflicts and enhances unity among staff members, which contributes to smoother administrative operations. To Lunenburg (2010), participatory decision-making improves educational effectiveness by strengthening interpersonal relationships and teamwork.

In addition, teachers' participation enhances students' engagement and discipline through well-managed sports programmes. When teachers contribute to decisions about sports activities, they are better positioned to design programmes that meet students' interests and developmental needs. This increases student participation and fosters positive behaviours such as teamwork,

respect and leadership (Ololube, 2024). Well-organized sports programmes also serve as constructive outlets for students' energy, thereby reducing disciplinary issues and supporting a conducive learning environment. This, in turn, enhances the effectiveness of school administration (Bailey, 2006; Coakley, 2015; Mahoney, 2000; Marsh & Kleitman, 2003).

However, the extent of teachers' participation in decision-making regarding sports and games is sometimes limited. In many public senior secondary schools, decisions about sports programmes are often centralized, with minimal input from teachers. This can lead to poorly planned activities, underutilization of resources, and low teacher commitment. When teachers are excluded from decision-making, they may feel less responsible for the success of sports programmes, which can negatively affect their implementation. However, Hoy and Miskel (2013) emphasized that lack of teachers participation reduces staff morale and hinder effectiveness.

According to Ololube (2017), teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in sports and games enhances effective administration to a large extent. It improves planning and organization, promotes efficient use of resources, promotes collaboration among staff and supports student development. Conversely, Ololube further noted that to make the most of the benefits depends on the extent to which schools create opportunities for meaningful teacher involvement and provide the necessary support for active participation.

Teachers' Participation in School-Based Decision-Making in the Area of School Timetable Scheduling and Effective Administration of Public Senior Secondary Schools

Teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in timetable scheduling plays a vital role in enhancing the effective administration of public senior secondary schools. The school timetable is a key administrative instrument that coordinates teaching and learning activities, allocates instructional time, and ensures the efficient use of human and physical resources. Because of its complexity, involving multiple subjects, teachers, and constraints, effective timetable construction requires collaboration between school administrators and teachers to achieve optimal outcomes Educational Timetabling (Ceschia et al., 2022).

To a large extent, teachers' participation in timetable scheduling enhances administrative effectiveness by promoting fairness in workload distribution. Teachers are directly involved in classroom instruction and are therefore best positioned to provide insights into subject demands, teaching loads, and student learning patterns (Ololube, 2017). Their involvement ensures that no teacher is overburdened while others are underutilized, thereby improving job satisfaction and productivity. Research shows that participatory decision-making in schools improves organizational efficiency by ensuring that decisions reflect the perspectives of those directly affected (Somech, 2010).

Furthermore, teachers' participation improves instructional quality and the effective use of teaching time. When teachers are involved in designing the timetable, they can recommend appropriate time slots for subjects based on student concentration levels and subject complexity. This helps reduce fatigue and enhances student comprehension and performance. Studies on school time utilization have shown that effective time allocation is strongly linked to improved educational outcomes and administrative efficiency in secondary schools (Inegbedion et al., 2020).

To a moderate extent, teachers' involvement in timetable scheduling also strengthens communication and collaboration among staff. Timetable planning requires coordination across

departments, subjects, and grade levels. When teachers participate in this process, it promotes dialogue, reduces scheduling conflicts, and fosters mutual understanding. This collaborative approach enhances teamwork and contributes to a more harmonious school environment. According to Lunenburg (2010), participative decision-making enhances organizational effectiveness by improving communication and shared responsibility among stakeholders.

In addition, teachers' participation increases flexibility and adaptability in school administration. Schools often face challenges such as limited classroom space, teacher shortages, and overlapping academic and extracurricular activities (Ololube, 2017). Teachers' input helps administrators design more realistic timetables that accommodate these constraints while maintaining instructional quality.

Moreover, teachers' involvement in timetable decisions enhances their sense of ownership and commitment to implementation. When teachers are part of the decision-making process, they are more likely to accept and adhere to the final timetable, reducing resistance and conflicts. This improves discipline, punctuality, and compliance with instructional schedules. Participatory management literature confirms that involvement in decision-making increases teacher motivation and job satisfaction, which are essential for effective school administration (Tijani, 2020).

However, the extent of teachers' participation in timetable scheduling is often limited in many public senior secondary schools. In several cases, principals or administrative officers make final decisions with minimal teacher input. This centralized approach may lead to unrealistic or overloaded timetables that do not reflect classroom realities, resulting in inefficiencies and dissatisfaction among staff. Additionally, lack of training in scheduling techniques and absence of structured participatory frameworks further limit meaningful teacher involvement. Therefore, promoting inclusive decision-making structures is essential for achieving efficient and effective school administration in secondary education systems (Ololube, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. This design is suitable as it allowed for the collection of data from a large group of respondents to examine and evaluate teachers' participation in decision-making processes for the effective administration of public senior secondary schools. This design helped in gathering quantitative data that was analyzed to understand trends, patterns, and relationships among variables.

The population for this study comprised of three hundred and thirty-five (335) principals and five thousand, nine hundred and twelve (5,912) teachers in the 335 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In all, the population of this study comprised of six thousand, two hundred and forty-seven (6,247) principals and teachers from the 23 Local Government Areas in Rivers State. (Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board: Nov. 2024).

The sample size comprised of 168 principals representing 50% of the total population of the principals, and 592 teachers, representing 10% of the total population of teachers. Specifically, the sample size comprise of 760 respondents. The stratified and the simple random sampling techniques were used in the selection of sample size of the study.

The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire entitled, "Teachers' Participation in School-Based Decision-Making in Discipline, Sports and Timetable Scheduling and Effective Administration Questionnaire" (TPSBDMDSTSEAQ). The instrument was

designed by the researcher and consisted of two main sections: Section A: Demographic information of respondents while Section B; included 30 item-statements addressing the research questions of the study. This section included 4-point modified Likert's-scale ranging from: Very High Extent (VHE) = 4 Points, High Extent (HE) = 3 Points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 Points, and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 Point, respectively.

The instrument was subjected to content and face validation by the researcher's supervisor and two other experts in the Department of Educational Management, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Their feedback was used to refine the items, ensuring they accurately captured the subject matter of the study.

The reliability of the instrument was established using the Cronbach Alpha to determine the internal consistency of the items. A test-retest method was used for this purpose. Specifically, twenty (20) copies was administered on 20 teachers and principals (10 copies each) who were not part of the sample size of the study, but are part of the population of the study. The same copies was re-administered to the twenty (20) respondents after an interval of two weeks. Thereafter, the data from the two (2) sets of the respondents was collated and analyzed with the use of Cronbach alpha to obtain a reliability index of .88, presenting that the instrument was .888 percent reliable.

The researcher administered seven hundred and sixty (760) copies of the instrument on seven hundred and sixty (760) respondents with the aid of three (3) trained research assistant. Upon retrieval, 711 copies, representing 94 % return rate of the administered instrument were completely filled and returned. The returned instruments comprised 143 principals and 568 teachers. The retrieved copies of the instrument was used for data analysis.

The Mean and Standard Deviation descriptive tools were used to analyze the research questions, using a Criterion Mean of 2.50 while the independent t-test inferential tool was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance; and with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 23.

RESULTS

Answer to Research Questions

Research Question 1: To what extent does teachers' participation in decision-making in the area of school discipline enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of Principals' and Teachers' Responses on the Extent Teachers' Participation in Decision-Making in the Area of School Discipline Enhances Administrative Effectiveness of Public Secondary Schools

S/N	Item Statements	Principals (N=143)		Teachers (N=568)		Mean Set $\bar{x}_1 + \bar{x}_2$	Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂		
3	Teachers are regularly consulted when developing discipline policies.	3.19	0.74	3.55	0.69	3.37	High Extent
4	Teacher input is valued in decisions regarding student disciplinary actions.	3.48	0.71	2.99	1.03	3.23	High Extent
5	Teachers participate in setting standards for	3.47	0.60	3.59	0.49	3.53	High Extent

	student behavior.						
6	Teachers contribute ideas during meetings on school discipline issues.	3.27	0.74	3.35	0.82	3.31	High Extent
7	Involving teachers in discipline-related decisions improves student behavior outcomes.	3.34	0.73	3.58	0.68	3.46	High Extent
8	Teachers feel empowered to address student discipline issues within school guidelines.	3.45	0.69	3.33	0.70	3.39	High Extent
Grand mean		3.37	0.70	3.40	0.72	3.39	High Extent

Research question 1 examined the extent to which teachers' participation in decision-making in the area of school discipline enhances effective administration of public senior secondary schools. Based on the result in Table 1, the following holds true: The overall mean score (\bar{x} set = 3.39) for the combined responses of principals and teachers indicating a high extent of agreement that teachers' participation in discipline-related decision-making enhances administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools. The item specific analysis also shows principals and teachers agreeing to each of the items to a high extent. Principals consistently scored items slightly lower (Grand Mean $\bar{x}_1 = 3.37$) than teachers (Grand Mean $\bar{x}_2 = 3.40$), indicating that teachers might perceive their participation more slightly more impactful than principals do. The standard deviation values for both groups are relatively low ($SD_1 = 0.70$, $SD_2 = 0.72$), suggesting minimal variability in responses and a high level of agreement among participants.

The results show that teachers' participation in decision-making on school discipline is perceived to significantly enhance administrative effectiveness in public senior secondary schools. Key aspects, such as developing discipline policies, contributing to standards for behavior, and addressing discipline issues within guidelines, highlight the importance of involving teachers in this area.

Research Question 2: To what extent do teachers' participation in decision-making in the area of sports and games enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of Principals' and Teachers' Responses on the Extent Teachers' Participation in Decision-Making in the Area of Sports and Games Enhances Administrative Effectiveness of Public Secondary Schools

S/N	Item Statements	Principals (N=143)		Teachers (N=568)		Mean Set	Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD_1	\bar{x}_2	SD_2		
9	Teachers are included in the planning of sports and games activities.	3.68	0.46	3.54	0.62	2	High Extent
10	Teachers help to develop schedules for sports events in the school.	3.87	0.34	3.22	0.80	3.55	High Extent
11	Teachers' opinions are considered in selecting school teams and organizing competitions.	3.38	0.79	3.52	0.58	3.45	High Extent
12	Teachers contribute to decisions about funding and resources for sports programs.	2.73	1.19	3.23	0.90	2.98	High Extent
13	Teachers' involvement in sports and games decisions positively impacts student	2.95	0.86	3.62	0.59	3.28	High Extent

14	participation. Teachers can suggest new sports or activities to include in the school's program.	2.71	1.02	3.44	0.62	3.08	High Extent
Grand mean		3.22	0.78	3.43	0.69	3.33	High Extent

The research question 2 examined the extent to which teachers' participation in decision-making in the area of sports and games enhances the effective administration of public senior secondary schools. Based on the analysis in Table 2, the overall mean score for principals and teachers combined (\bar{x} set=3.33) indicates a high extent of agreement that teachers' participation in decision-making in the area of sports and games enhances the administrative effectiveness of public senior secondary schools. The grand mean score for principals ($\bar{x}_1 = 3.22$) is slightly lower than that of teachers ($\bar{x}_2 = 3.43$), indicating that teachers perceive their participation in sports and games decision-making as more impactful than principals do. The standard deviation for both groups ($SD_1 = 0.78$, $SD_2 = 0.69$) is relatively low, showing consistency in responses within each group.

The results indicate that teachers' participation in decision-making related to sports and games is perceived to enhance the effective administration of public senior secondary schools to a high extent with a combined grand mean set (\bar{x} set) of 3.33. While the overall response is positive, the item on contributing to funding and resources for sports programs (item 13) received the lowest mean, suggesting an area for potential improvement in involving teachers more actively in resource allocation decisions.

Research Question 3: To what extent do teachers' participation in decision-making in the area of school timetable schedules enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of Principals' and Teachers' Responses on the Extent Teachers' Participation in Decision-Making in the Area of School Timetable Schedules Enhances Administrative Effectiveness of Public Secondary Schools

S/N	Item Statements	Principals (N=143)		Teachers (N=568)		Mean Set	Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD_1	\bar{x}_2	SD_2		
15	Teachers are involved in developing the school timetable.	3.16	1.04	3.38	0.84	2	High Extent
16	Teachers' preferences for class periods are considered during timetable planning.	3.31	0.98	3.15	0.82	3.23	High Extent
17	The administration consults teachers on how timetable changes affect their workload.	3.01	0.86	3.45	0.59	3.23	High Extent
18	Teachers participate in discussions about optimizing class schedules for student learning.	3.24	2.55	3.57	0.57	3.41	High Extent
19	Teachers' input on the timetable contributes to better time management in the school.	3.04	0.91	3.52	0.74	3.28	High Extent
20	Teachers have opportunities to request adjustments to the timetable when needed.	3.06	0.80	3.26	0.74	3.16	High Extent
Grand mean		3.14	1.19	3.39	0.72	3.26	High Extent

The research question 3 sought to determine the extent to which teachers' participation in decision-making in the area of school timetable schedules enhances the effective administration of public senior secondary schools. Based on the analysis in Table 3, the combined grand mean score (\bar{x} set=3.26) indicates a high extent of agreement that teachers' participation in decision-making on school timetable schedules enhances administrative effectiveness. Although principals and teachers differ slightly in their item specific analysis, the grand mean for each group indicates agreement with each of the items to a high extent. The grand mean for principals ($\bar{x}_1 = 3.14$) is slightly lower than that for teachers ($\bar{x}_2 = 3.39$), indicating that teachers perceive their participation as more impactful compared to principals' perception. The standard deviations are generally low, particularly for teachers ($SD_2 = 0.72$), suggesting consistent responses. However, the higher standard deviation for principals ($SD_1 = 1.19$) indicates greater variability in their perceptions.

The results indicate that teachers' participation in timetable-related decision-making is perceived to enhance administrative effectiveness to a high extent. Strong agreement was observed regarding teachers' involvement in optimizing schedules for student learning and contributing to time management. Some areas, such as opportunities for teachers to request adjustments to timetables show slightly lower levels of agreement, suggesting potential for improvement in fostering teacher flexibility.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of principals and teachers on the extent teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school discipline enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: T-test analysis of the mean rating of principals' and teachers responses on the extent of teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school discipline enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Respondents	N	Mean	SD	t	df	P-value
Principals	143	3.37	.1198	-2.98	709	.771
Teachers	568	3.40	.2308			

Data in Table 4 shows the independent samples t-test analysis of the mean rating of principals and teachers on the extent of teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school discipline enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. From the Table, principals had a grand mean of 3.37 and standard deviation of .1198 while teachers had a mean score of 3.40 and standard deviation of .2308. A t-value of -2.98 was obtained and a p-value of .771, which is greater than .05. This indicates that the difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers is not statistically significant. Since the P-value (.771) is greater than the significance level (.05), we fail to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of principals and teachers on the extent to which teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school discipline enhances effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The alignment in perceptions between principals and teachers may suggest that both groups recognize the importance of involving teachers in discipline-related decision-making processes. This could be attributed to well-established policies and practices in many schools

where teachers are routinely consulted on matters of discipline. Additionally, there may be a shared understanding of how teacher involvement positively impacts discipline policies and outcomes, leading to similar evaluations.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Principals and teachers on the extent teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of sports and games enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: T-test analysis of the mean rating of principals' and teachers' responses on the extent of teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of sports and games enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Respondents	N	Mean	SD.	t	df	P-value
Principals	143	3.22	.4966	-.974	709	.371
Teachers	568	3.43	.1676			

Data in Table 5 shows the independent samples t- test analysis of the mean rating of principals and teachers on the extent of teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of sports and games enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. With a mean score of 3.22, standard deviation of .4966 for principals; mean score of 3.43 and standard deviation of .1676 for teachers respectively. A t-value of -.974 and p-value of .371, being greater than .05, indicates that the difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers is not statistically significant. Since the p-value (.371) is greater than the significance level (.05), we fail to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, it is concluded that there is **no** significant difference in the mean rating of principals and teachers on the extent to which teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of sports and games enhances effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The lack of significant difference could stem from a uniform acknowledgment of teachers' roles in planning and organizing sports and games. This might indicate that schools already have collaborative structures in place for sports-related decision-making. Both principals and teachers similarly perceive the benefits of involving teachers in these decisions, such as improved student participation and better resource management.

H0₃: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of principals and teachers on the extent teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school time-table schedules enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: t- test analysis of the mean rating of principals' and teachers' responses on the extent of teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area of school time-table schedules enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Respondents	N	Mean	SD	t	df	P-value
Principals	143	3.14	.1204	-3.082	709	.132
Teachers	568	3.39	.1597			

Data in Table 6 shows the independent samples t- test analysis of the mean rating of principals and teachers on the extent of teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the area

of school Time-table schedules enhance effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. With a mean score of 3.14 and standard deviation of .1204 for principals and mean score of 3.39 and standard deviation of .1597 for teachers, a t-value of -3.082 and a p-value of .132, being greater than .05, the result show that a significant statistical difference does not exist between principals' and teachers' mean rating. Since the p-value of .132 is greater than the significance level (.05), we fail to reject the null hypothesis. The absence of significant difference may suggest that both principals and teachers acknowledge the necessity of teacher participation in timetable-related decisions. Principals may recognize that involving teachers ensures smoother implementation of timetables and better accommodation of teachers' preferences and workloads. On the other hand, teachers might feel their contributions to timetable decisions are acknowledged and valued, leading to a shared perspective on its impact on administrative effectiveness. This shared understanding may result from established collaborative practices in timetable scheduling within many schools.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Teachers' Participation in School-Based Decision-Making in the Area of School Discipline

The findings of the current study as presented on Table 1 indicated that the mean rating for teachers' participation in school discipline was relatively high, with principals and teachers giving similar responses. The t-test analysis on Table 4 yielded a p-value of .771, which is greater than the .05 significance level, meaning the null hypothesis could not be rejected. This suggests that there is no significant difference in the perceptions of principals and teachers regarding the impact of teacher participation in school discipline on effective administration.

These results align with the work of Ololube (2017), who also found that teacher involvement in developing disciplinary policies led to fewer incidents of student indiscipline and higher student compliance. Bush (2015) further corroborates these findings, by emphasizing that teacher participation in policy formulation, particularly in discipline, contributed to more effective administrative outcomes. The lack of significant difference in this study suggests that both principals and teachers generally agree on the importance of teacher involvement in maintaining school discipline, mirroring findings from other studies, such as Cotton (2000), who also observed positive impacts on student discipline with teacher participation. Similarly, Hoy and Miskel (2013) also found that teacher participation in decision-making positively impacted school discipline, enhancing both teacher morale and the school environment. The current study strengthens this understanding by focusing on how teachers' input in decisions directly related to discipline can lead to a more structured and effective school environment.

Teachers' Participation in School-Based Decision-Making in the Area of Sports and Games

The findings as presented in Table 2 and 5 respectively, the t-test revealed a p-value of .371, which is greater than .05, meaning the null hypothesis is not rejected. This indicates no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers regarding the impact of teachers' participation in sports and games on school administration. These results align with Bailey (2006), Coakley (2015), Mahoney (2000) and Marsh and Kleitman (2003), whose study found that teacher participation in decision-making regarding sports programmes, resulted in better-organized activities and higher student engagement. While the present study did not show

a significant difference, it is possible that the level of involvement of teachers in sports-related decisions varies across schools. Therefore, enhancing teacher participation might lead to better outcomes if teachers are more consistently engaged in organizing and planning sports activities.

Teachers' Participation in School-Based Decision-Making in the Area of School Time-Table Schedules

The p-value for hypothesis 3 as presented in Table 6 was found to be .132, which is greater than the .05 significance level, meaning that the null hypothesis could not be rejected. This suggests that there is no significant difference in the perception of principals and teachers regarding the role of teachers' participation in timetable scheduling in promoting effective school administration. This aligns with studies such as Inegbedion et al. (2020) and Ololube (2017), both of which emphasize the importance of involving teachers in timetable creation. These studies argue that when teachers are involved, class schedules are better aligned with the actual learning needs of students, improving overall school administration. Similarly, Lunenburg (2010) and Tijani (2020) found that teacher input in scheduling contributed to reduced absenteeism and improved teacher-student relationships. In this regard, the present study's findings suggest that teacher participation in timetable scheduling is widely viewed as critical for administrative efficiency.

CONCLUSION

This study has successfully examined teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in discipline, sports and timetable scheduling as predictors of effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study concludes that teachers' participation in school-based decision-making in the areas of discipline, sports and games, and timetable scheduling significantly enhances the effective administration of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings indicated that when teachers are actively involved in disciplinary decisions, schools experience improved order, fairness, and consistency in rule enforcement. Similarly, participation in sports and games promotes better organization of co-curricular activities, strengthens student engagement, and supports a positive school climate. In the area of timetable scheduling, teachers' involvement ensures fair workload distribution, improved instructional planning, and reduced scheduling conflicts. On the whole, the study affirmed that participatory decision-making promotes collaboration, improves communication, and increases teachers' commitment to school goals.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

- School administrators should ensure that teachers are actively involved in decision-making processes, particularly in areas of discipline, sports and games, and timetable scheduling, to promote shared responsibility and improve administrative effectiveness in public senior secondary schools.
- The Ministry of Education and school management boards should establish formal structures such as functional committees and regular consultative meetings that

encourage meaningful teacher participation in school governance and policy implementation.

- Regular capacity-building programmes such as workshops and seminars should be organized for teachers to enhance their leadership, planning, and decision-making skills, enabling them to contribute more effectively to school administration processes.

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